

ACCST Research Journal

ISSN 0972-7779

Volume - XXI, No. 3, July 2023

Journal website: www.internationaljournalsiwan.com

ORCID Link: <https://orcid.org/0009-0008-6661-0289>

Google Scholar: <https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=KJ4eXesAAAAJ&hl=en>

Refereed and Peer-Reviewed Quarterly Journal

Adoption of Digital Marketing in MSME: A Case Study of Bihar

by **Md. Israr Hassan Khan**, *Professor & Head,*

P.G. Centre of Commerce,

Sri Arvind Mahila College, Kazipur, Patna-800004, India

&

Juhi Kumari, *Research Scholar,*

P.G. Department of Commerce

Email: juhik5647@gmail.com

(Received: June 16, 2023; Accepted: July 17, 2023;

Published Online: July 31, 2023)

Ignoring digital marketing is like representing your business without any audience. *✍ Jason Matthew*

Abstract:

Digitalization has become Part of our daily routines. It is shaping the traditional way in which Consumers and business interact with each other. The present study emphasized on assessing the Challenges faced by MSME in adoption of Digital Marketing.

The review will be based on Secondary data Sources. The database required for the study would be published and unpublished report, documents from various websites and personal observations. This study had identified

[6]

Market Competition, poor infrastructure, Lack of adequate awareness and Skill, Knowledge deficiencies and attitude towards ICT adoption as impediments which are required to be handled efficiently and effectively.

Keywords: Digital Marketing, ICT, Social Media, MSME, Economy

Introduction:

The MSMEs stand for Micro, small and medium Enterprises, and the role of these Industries in the growing economy of developing Countries is very Crucial. Bihar is one of the Major homes of MSME Sector in India; with nearly 95% of its Industries falling under the Particular Category, notwithstanding only 5% of these industries are exposed to Banks. Despite the Government of India releasing press reports reviewing the year end success story of MSMEs and their employment generation. Bihar MSMEs have to face many difficulties in adoption of Digital Marketing. The main reasons are lack of knowledge in use of digital marketing, financial issues, Lack of technical expertise, dearth of latest information and lack of market and infrastructure, inadequate and unreliable power supply.

Digitalization has become Part of our daily routines. The role of Digital Marketing in MSME is to improve market demand and efficiency of firm. Digital Marketing makes easy to brand promotion and distribution. In changing Digital Marketing, the MSME sector tries to implement the most useful marketing strategies like blogging, social media, email marketing, SEO and more. The implementation of the strategy is constantly churned and innovated because no one really knows what strategy will click for which business that's why Digital Marketing is backbone of Bihar MSMEs. Digital marketing not only passes the message but also receives and exchange perception and idea in short span of time.

Background and Problem Formulation:

The past decade have observed a quick globalization of economic activity and this globalization process has increased the significance of Digital marketing. Digital marketing is beneficial for MSME, from promotion to services.

The major problem of Bihar MSMEs is lack of technical expertise, skills and awareness about digitalization, difficulty in obtaining capital. Digital marketing provides best platform for all enterprises.

Conceptual Framework :

A micro enterprise is a business with an investment of not more than Rs. 1 crore and a Rs. 5 crore turnover, a small unit is one with an investment of not more than Rs. 10 crore and a Rs. 50 crore turnover, and a medium unit is one with an investment not exceeding Rs. 50 crore and a Rs. 250 crore turnover.

Study Area:

Bihar is a state of east India. It is divided by the river Ganga, which floods its fertile plains. Patna is the capital of Bihar. MSME Development institute Patna, a field office of development commissioner under the ministry of MSME is the nodal office for the state of Bihar having another office located at Muzaffarpur in 1957. The jurisdictional are of MSME-DI, Patna consist of 17 districts of Bihar namely Patna, Arwal, Aurangabad, Banka, Bhabhua, Buxar, Gaya, Jamui, Jhanabad, Lakhisarai, Munger, Nawada, Rohatas and Sheikhpura. In this paper, we want to be study in Patna.

Study Rationale and Relevance:

Digital marketing provides a wide range of benefits to MSME business such as brand popularity, improved sales and revenue better customer reach and much more. The future scope if digital marketing in Bihar MSME is that there will be more points of contact. We visualized a future where digital marketing in MSME is much more growing. Other factors for significance of study are as below:

- Better outcome for promotional goals.
- Digital marketing is more cost effective as compared to traditional marketing.
- Easy, flexible.
- High engagement.
- Small investments and big returns.
- Enable to capture.

Objectives:

This research is to develop a clear understanding about the existing research related to MSME and digital marketing. This paper aims to empirically explore the adoption of digital marketing in MSME sector Bihar. The main objectives of this research are to know the following points:

- To study present status of Digital Marketing as practiced by Bihar MSME.

- To find the types of problem have to face by MSMEs.
- To identify some important issues challenges and constraints confronted by these enterprises and to offer suggestion to overcome the same.
- To compare the perceived and actual benefits and barriers of using Digital Marketing.

Hypothesis:

The research topic is associated with Digital Marketing in MSME: A case study of Bihar. The present research has following hypothesis.

H1. There is some problem of finance in all type of industries.

H0. There is no problem of finance in all type of industries.

H1. There is problem in challenges faced by Bihar MSME.

H0. There is no problem in challenges faced by Bihar MSME.

Problems:

The adoption of digital marketing in MSMEs can be challenging due to several common problems:

Lack of Awareness and Knowledge- Many MSME owner and employees may lack digital marketing skill and knowledge, making it difficult to implement effective online strategies.

Competition- Patna's MSME Sector can be highly competitive, making it challenging for smaller businesses to stand out effectively in digital space.

Lack of Strategy- Some MSMEs may engage in digital marketing without clear strategy, leading to ineffective campaigns and wasted resources.

Technological Evolution- The rapid pace of technological change requires MSMEs to continually adapt to new digital marketing tools and platforms.

Trust and Security Concerns- Online security and trust issues may deter MSMEs from engaging in e-commerce or sharing customer data online.

Prospects :

Increased Reach- MSMEs can use digital marketing to potentially reach a wider audience, including domestic and international markets, which improves their chances of growing.

Cost Efficiency- Digital marketing can be more economical than traditional marketing, allowing MSMEs to better allocate their limited resources.

Customer Engagement- Social media platforms give MSMEs the opportunity to interact with clients directly, forge bonds, and receive input to improve their goods and services.

Local and Global Visibility- MSMEs in Patna can utilize digital marketing to highlight their distinctive offers not only locally but also internationally, drawing in a wide range of clients.

Research Methodology:

The main purpose of the present study is to determine the digital marketing adoption in Bihar MSME. The study will be based upon secondary data sources.

The database required for the study would be:

- ❖ Published reports, documents from various government and private sources.
- ❖ Relevant websites.
- ❖ Newspaper and other weekly and monthly magazines.
- ❖ Relevant Maps of study area.

Secondary Data Sources:

Information will be collected from various departments associated with MSMEs.

- Books, Journal, Previous Research Materials, etc.
- Reports of RBI.
- Annual reports of MSME.

The data would be analyzed by various qualitative and quantitative statistical techniques. Method will be descriptive, historical, analytical, case study method and also geographical image for better results. Different graph, chart and diagram will also use for comprehensive presentation.

Findings and Suggestions:

MSMEs are critical for fostering economic growth, innovation, and inclusive development in both developing and developed economies. They are dynamic and play vital role in job creation and economic stability. MSMEs in Patna may need to invest in training, allocate budgets for digital marketing, adapt to changing technologies and seek professional guidance. Collaboration with digital marketing agencies or consultants can also be beneficial.

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